

The power of prosumers in publishing

Möbius is an initiative funded under the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme that aims to modernize the European book publishing industry by remodelling the traditional value chains and business models uncovering the prosumers potential and delivering new enriched media experiences.

Möbius book experience

An immersive and interactive book experience through the Möbius Player, using binaural reproduction. Individuals will be able to use the Möbius App for immersive reading and to enjoy the social interaction features.

Möbius book art installation

A fixed immersive installation including experiences of about 15 minutes each will be produced by experienced immersive artists trained at the Gianfranco Iannuzzi School and in the visualization of stories.

Learn more about Möbius!

Immersive book box

Möbius will design and construct a projection space, to be explored by 4-5 people at a time. The walls will be transparent tissue screens, allowing projections to shine through from the outside, and a 3D audio installation will to be adapted for allowing a truly immersive experience.

Möbius book VR experience

The Möbius book box will be adapted to VR-headsets, to provide a convenient user-experience without the need for any installation, being made available via social media for easy download to own VRs.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 957185.